

Surgical utility of K-Wire in Orthopaedic Surgery

Chandru R, Venkatachalam K*

Department of Orthopaedic Surgery, Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre (Affiliated to The Tamilnadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Chennai),
Tiruchirappalli, INDIA.

Abstract

Kirschner wires are aseptic, refined, sleek stainless steel wires employed in Orthopaedic Surgery as implants. K-wire implants are very adaptable and may effectively heal fractures of various types in nearly all appendicular bones. The aim of this study is to evaluate the versatile uses of K-Wire in fracture fixation of the Appendicular skeletal system and to ascertain their efficacy and dependability of fracture fixation. This was a prospective cross sectional interventional study. 50 patients with appendicular fracture of both upper and lower limb and open fractures until Gustilo-Anderson Type II, who had attended Orthopaedic Surgery out-patient Department or Casualty, within 10 days of injury, were included in the study. All patients were operated using K-wire fixation. Post-operatively Pain, Visual Analogue Scores (VAS) and Range of Movement (ROM) scores, were recorded, at the end of 3 months. We had 50 patients who had appendicular fracture of the upper limb or lower limb. Mean (SD) age of the patients was 34.28 (20.35) years. 62% were female 38% were males. 26 (52%) patients had radius and ulna fracture, 7 (14%) had humerus fracture, 6 (12%) had malleolar fracture, 4 (8%) had calcaneal fracture, 3 (6%) had metatarsal fracture, 3 (6%) had ulnar olecranon fracture and 1 (2%) had patellar fracture. Pre-operative mean (SD) Visual Analogue Scores (VAS) and Range of Movement (ROM) was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) than Post-op. There was a pre-ponderance of upper extremity appendicular fractures at ($n=36$; 72%). The utilization of K-wire fixation for appendicular fractures of the upper and lower limb is an effective surgical approach, to achieve reduction and achieve union. Apart from being cost-effective, with minimal blood-loss, they are very much patient compliant and has ease of implant exit. Close reduction, C-Arm confirmation of reduction and choice of appropriateness of the site of fixation are of paramount importance. The versatile utility of K-wire in Orthopaedic Surgery has been historically acknowledged and is well documented. Our experience acknowledges the same profound view.

Keywords: Appendicular Skeletal fractures, K wire fixation, “J” bend in K wire.

Introduction

The K-wire, developed by Martin Kirschner in 1909, was originally a large, smooth pin with a diamond-shaped tip of 3.5 to 6 mm in diameter (1). It was used as a Nagel extension for skeletal traction in cases of lengthy bone fractures, using the same idea as Steinmann's nail. Nevertheless, the utilization of robust pins necessitated the prior drilling of holes, into which the wire was forcefully inserted, resulting in the undesirable consequence of bone heating and necrosis causing infection, due to the back-and-forth motion of the pin (2). Since the introduction of external accordion-like devices in 1927, it has been feasible to insert thin wires with diameters ranging from 0.7 to 1.5 mm without the need for pre-drilling. This has led to a solid fixation and a decrease in the occurrence of pin tract infection (3). Starting in 1935, it was employed for the purpose of maintaining and reducing fracture-dislocations, particularly in the elbow, hip and ankle. K-wires were first utilized in 1937 to treat hand fractures, which yet remains its primary application even today (4).

In 1940, Murray performed the initial intra-medullary implantation of a K-wire, to cure a clavicle fracture (5). Subsequently, this concept was expanded for application in fractures of the radius, ulna, fibula, metacarpal and metatarsal bones, particularly during World War II (6). The manual hand drill was substituted with a motorized power drill, offering enhanced accuracy and resolving numerous problems (7). Kirschner wires, sometimes known as K-wires, are very adaptable for the purpose of fixing fractures. K-wires are useful for both immediate temporary and delayed temporary fixation of appendicular bone fractures (1). The complications linked with the wrong usage of K-wiring technique, ranges from mild to potentially fatal. Multiple instances in the literature document catastrophic complications resulting from the remote migration of a K-wire to important structures, including the heart, thoracic major arteries, and lungs (8). Minor difficulties can significantly contribute to parental concern and lengthen patients' recovery, however they are usually underestimated in terms of reporting (8). The objective of this study is to assess the diverse and successful application of K-Wire in fractures of the Appendicular skeletal system and to determine the effectiveness and reliability of fracture fixation.

Materials and Methods

Study design and population

This prospective cross-sectional interventional study was done in the Department of Orthopaedics at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli South India, which is tertiary health care centre. It was done from November 2023 to April

2024. Fifty (50) patients, both male and female more than 3 years of age, with appendicular fracture of both upper limb and lower limb and open fractures until Gustilo-Anderson Type II who attended the Orthopaedic Surgery outpatient Department or Casualty, within 10 days of injury were included in the study. Those with pathological fractures were excluded from the study. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional ethical committee (Ref. No: 1136/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2023 – IEC 159, dated 26.10.2023). Informed written consent were obtained from the patient and in case of paediatric patients, from the parents.

Outcomes and measures

In all patients pre-operative demographic data was collected and recorded in the proforma. Pre-operative work-up including pain Visual Analogue Scores (VAS) and Range of Movement (ROM), percentage were recorded. All patients were operated using K-wire fixation technique. Post-operative Pain, Visual Analogue Scores (VAS) and Range of Movement (ROM) scores were recorded at the end of 3 months. Thus the recruitment of patients was for 6 months and follow-up was till July 2024.

Statistical analysis

The mean value, together with the standard deviation, was calculated for the time period spanning from pre-operative to post-operative after a minimum Post-Operative duration of 3 months. The change in the mean values from the pre-operative to the post-operative period was calculated using the Student's t-test for paired samples.

Results

We had 50 patients who had appendicular fracture of the upper limb or lower limb. They were treated by K wire fixation. Mean (SD) age of the patients was 34.28 (20.35) years. Thirty One (31) of the 50 patients were female (62%) and 19 of the 50 patients were males (38%). We found that 26 (52%) patients had radius and ulna fracture, 7 (14%) had humerus fracture, 6 (12%) had malleolar fracture, 4 (8%) had calcaneal fracture, 3 (6%) had metatarsal fracture, 3 (6%) had ulnar olecranon fracture and 1 (2%) had patellar fracture (Table 1). Thus there was a pre-ponderance of upper extremity fracture (72%; n = 36).

Pre-operative mean (SD) Visual Analogue Score (VAS) 7.16 (1.46) was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) than post-op mean (SD) Visual Analogue Score (VAS) 2.48 (1.15) (Figure 1). Pre-operative mean (SD) Range of Movement (ROM) percentage 40.6 (14.49) was significantly lower ($p < 0.0001$) than post-op mean (SD) range of movement percentage 80.2 (14.36) (Figure 2-8).

Table 1. Distribution and zone of appendicular fracture

No.	Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
1	Radius and ulna fracture	26	52
2	Humerus fracture	7	14
3	Malleolar fracture	6	12
4	Metatarsal fracture	4	8
5	Calcaneal fracture	3	6
6	Ulnar olecranon fracture	3	6
7	Patellar fracture	1	2

Figure 1. Pre-op and Post-op VAS and ROM**Figure 2. Pre-op and Post-op X-rays of an 8-year-old boy with distal radius fracture treated by multiple K wire fixation**

Figure 3. Pre-op and Post-op X-rays of tension band wiring of left patellar fracture in a 52 year female

Figure 4: X-ray of a 34 year old female patient Calcaneal fracture fixed with multiple K-wires

Figure 5: Pre-op and Post-op X-rays of a Proximal humerus fracture of a 11 year old female fixed with multiple K-wires

Figure 6: Post-op X-rays of a Medial malleolar fracture in a 38 year old female fixed with multiple K-wires

Figure 7: Pre-op and post-op X-rays of an Olecranon fracture in a 24 year old male fixed with multiple K-wires

Figure 8: Post-op X-ray of multiple Metatarsal fractures in a 30 year old male fixed with K-wires individually to restore length and alignment

Discussion

The Kirschner wire, also known as the K-wire, is a straightforward and cost-effective implant, that is essentially useful, for many an Orthopaedic operations (1). Developed by Martin Kirschner in 1909, the K-wire saw numerous revisions over the following century. However, it was during World War II that the K-wire saw significant advancements and new possibilities (1). Originally, it was implemented for the purpose of bone traction. Even today the Ilizarov uses K-wires, pre-tensioned with rings. In 1932, Otto Loewe, utilized it for the purpose of fracture repair, and in 1940, Frederick Powell employed it for tension band wire (9). Modern orthopaedic practices, particularly in the fields of paediatrics and hand Surgery, rely heavily on the usage of K-wires. Plate fixation procedures are frequently employed to stabilize fractures. However, K-wires offer a simpler and less intrusive option, especially in the hand and wrist where the anatomical features are well-suited for their application (10).

An advantage of using a K-wire, is that it may be inserted with relative ease, causing minimal damage to the soft tissue and tendons. However, the most significant benefit is the feasibility of painless percutaneous implantation. This procedure, known as closed reduction and external fixation, is less complex than open reduction and internal fixation. It carries less related hazards, reduces edema and stiffness, and continues to be the favored method in modern medicine (11). Percutaneous K-wire fixation provides a secure and inflexible fixation following appropriate alignment, enabling prompt movement to avoid long-term deformity and immobility (12). The most important factor is less blood loss and ease of implant exit.

Though percutaneous K-wire fixation reduces and potentially prevents complications that arise following open reduction and internal fixation. These complications include infection, impaired fracture healing, stiffness resulting from deep soft tissue dissection, fibrosis, impalement of tendons, loosening or breakage of the K-wire, and complex regional pain syndrome. Intramedullary metacarpal K-wire fixation is a straightforward technique that minimizes strain on the tendons (13).

In addition to its benefits, the utilization of K-wires, also has its limitations. The first writings discouraging the usage of K-wires were published in 1939. The migration of K-wires and the lack of stiffness and strength when employed in femoral neck fractures were explained (14). The first instances of K-wire migration from the clavicle to the lungs were documented in 1943 (15). K-wire migration remains a persistent issue that poses a significant difficulty due to its potential to induce severe consequences, ranging from non-fatal to devastating outcomes, and even death (16). The K-wires in the majority of the documented cases moved from the shoulder girdle to various locations such as the aorta, pulmonary

system, the trachea, the mediastinum, neck, spleen, and spinal canal. Additionally, there have been instances of migration from other anatomical places, such as migration from the hip to the heart, liver, or popliteal fossa. There have even been cases of migration from the left hand into the heart. The cause of K-wire migration remains unclear, however in most instances, migration can be averted by bending the distal end of the K-wire in a 'j' shaped fashion. However, it is important to note that even wires that are bent might still move after they break. Therefore, it is recommended to take frequent follow-up X-rays until the K-wires are exited out (17). In our series we had superficial infection in 5 cases (10%) which were controlled with oral antibiotics (Linezolid 600mg – BD for 5 days). All these cases were diabetic and were of Gustilo Anderson type II. We had no cases of K-wire breakage as we had immobilized all cases with a pop-slab or cast. We also did not have any cases of K-wire migration as we had followed the 'j' bend technique meticulously.

Pin track infections have been prevalent since the inception of the K-wire. This complexity was one of the causes that led to the creation of thinner K-wires. However, despite the use of smaller diameter K-wires, pin track infections continue to happen (18).

In 1954, Stone proposed a technique using sterile dressings with foam rubber anchors. These anchors are inserted at the site where the K-wire penetrates the skin, with the purpose of preventing skin necrosis and infection. One should not underestimate the occurrence of pin track infections (19). Currently, the utilization of K-wires may lead to pin track infections in approximately 2.2 to 21% of instances. This complexity may result in the need for premature removal of the pin, which could then lead to non-union. Promptly addressing pin track infection is crucial, whether through immobilization, administration of antibiotics, or extraction of loose pins. Reduced infection rates are observed when K-wires are implanted beneath the skin surface (20). A major factor is patient compliance of instructions.

Our study indicated a higher incidence of appendicular fractures in females (62%; n = 31) compared to males (38%; n = 19). We observed a rising prevalence of fractures in the upper limb and ulnar olecranon over old age, but we did not find a similar increase in fractures affecting the malleolar, calcaneal, or metatarsal bones, which aligns with earlier epidemiological studies. The many forms of fractures and their correlation with age and gender can be most effectively elucidated by the progression of bone deterioration and micro-architectural modifications that occur as one ages. Therefore, fractures that are prone to occur due to osteoporosis, such as fractures in the radius, ulna, and humerus, have a higher likelihood of happening in females and older individuals. Pain, Visual Analogue Scores (VAS) and Range of Movement (ROM) improved significantly following K wire insertion.

Limitations of this study

The limitations of this study are, it is a cross-sectional study with a relatively small sample size. More studies with a larger sample size and randomized studies will give a clearer picture of the Clinico-Functional outcome of K wire fixation. All said and done K-wires are and shall continue to be a valuable implant in Orthopaedic Surgery.

Conclusion

The utilization of K-wire fixation for appendicular fractures of the upper and lower limb is an effective approach for preventing re-displacement. We observed a notable improvement in Pain, Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Range of Motion (ROM), subsequent to the implantation of K-wires. It is crucial to identify the signs of instability in these fractures as they impact the final anatomical outcome. Variables such as age above 65, severe comminution, and open & grossly contaminated fractures, are linked to poor stability in K-wire fixation and unfavorable anatomical Clinico-Functional result. It is advisable to explore an alternative method of stabilization in order to enhance the stability of the fixation in these individuals. K-wires apart from fracture fixation are also used for temporary fixation, in Peadiatric Orthopaedics, osteotomies, external fixation, arthrodesis, tension band wiring and skeletal tension bound traction.

References

1. Rex C, Kumar MH, Premanand C, Kumar AS. A legendary implant that has stood the test of time and its current utilization. *J Orthoped Joint Surg.* 2022;4(1):35-39.
2. Netscher DT, Gharbaoui I. Hand and upper extremities. *Acute care Surg: Principles Practice.* 2007;17(3):615-655.
3. Sharma H, Taylor GR, Clarke NM. A review of K-wire related complications in the emergency management of paediatric upper extremity trauma. *Ann Roy Coll Surg Engl.* 2007;89(3):252-258.
4. Franssen BB, Schuurman AH, Van der Molen AM, Kon M. One century of Kirschner wires and Kirschner wire insertion techniques: a historical review. *Acta Orthop Belg.* 2010;76(1):1-6.
5. Bakota B, Chan G, Staresinic M, Rajput V, Phadnis J, Korac Z. Safe intramedullary fixation of displaced midshaft clavicle fractures with 2.5 mm Kirschner wires—technique description and a two-part versus multifragmentary fracture fixation outcome comparison. *Injury.* 2017;48(2):S27-33.

6. Franssen BB. Kirschner Wires: insertion techniques and bone related consequences. *Utrecht Univ.* 2010;4:1-6.
7. Portaccio I. Smart tools for Orthopaedic Surgery with sensing capability: a novel approach. *J Biol Regulat Homeostat Agents.* 2020;27(9):251-257.
8. Ostojic Z, Prlic J, Juka K, Ljubic B, Roth S, Bekavac J. Results of treatment of displaced supracondylar humeral fractures in children by K-wiring. *Collegium antropologicum.* 2010;34(1):239-242.
9. Mandal A, Gupta G. Role of K-wires in Orthopaedic Traumatology. In *Handbook of Orthopaedic Trauma Implantology.* Springer Nature Singapore. 2023;pp1-10.
10. Parmar R. Hand and Wrist Orthopaedic Injuries. *Orthopaedic Trauma in the Austere Environment: A Practical Guide to Care in the Humanitarian Setting.* 2016:513-526.
11. Sud V, Freeland AE. Skeletal fixation in digital replantation. *Microsurg.* 2002;22(4):165-171.
12. Wang W, Zeng M, Yang J, Wang L, Xie J, Hu Y. Clinical efficacy of closed reduction and percutaneous parallel K-wire interlocking fixation of first metacarpal base fracture. *J Orthoped Surg Res.* 2021;16:454-459.
13. Kyung MG, Lee SH, Kim MB. Complications related to implant fixation of patellar fractures: comparison of ring pins versus bent K-wires. *J Knee Surg.* 2017;30(6):560-564.
14. Rothermel SD, Aydogan U, Roush EP, Lewis GS. Proximal interphalangeal arthrodesis of lesser toes utilizing k-wires versus expanding implants: comparative biomechanical cadaveric study. *Foot Ankle Internat.* 2019;40(2):231-6.
15. Mazet R. Migration of a Kirschner wire from the shoulder region into the lung: report of two cases. *JBJS.* 1943;25(2):477-483.
16. Nakayama M, Gika M, Fukuda H, Yamahata T, Aoki K, Shiba S, Eguchi K. Migration of a Kirschner wire from the clavicle into the intrathoracic trachea. *Ann Thorac Surg.* 2009;88(2):653-654.
17. Mellado JM, Calmet J, Garcia Forcada IL, Sauri A, Gine J. Early intrathoracic migration of Kirschner wires used for percutaneous osteosynthesis of a two-part humeral neck fracture: a case report. *Emerg Radiol.* 2004;11:49-52.
18. Battle J, Carmichael KD. Incidence of pin track infections in children's fractures treated with Kirschner wire fixation. *J Pediatr Orthoped.* 2007;27(2):154-157.
19. Stone MM. Anchor and protector for Kirschner-wire skeletal traction. *JBJS.* 1954;36(4):874-875.

20. Ahmad A, Qureshi MA, Ali Z. Pin tract infection rates between percutaneous and buried K-wires in supracondylar fracture of humerus in children. Pak J Surg. 2010;26(2):146-150.
